

TEMPERATURE CONTROLLED HEATED 3-POINT BENDING SET-UP FOR ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

The operation of power products always leads to demanding conditions to the materials. Besides electrical requirements on insulation materials, high performance mechanical properties at increased temperatures are needed as well. This can be achieved by using fiber reinforced composites with a suitable resin system. This contribution describes a newly developed three-point bending set-up that is designed to enable a fast (within several minutes) and accurate ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) determination of the flexural strength and flexural modulus at elevated temperatures in accordance to various standards. FEM-simulations were required to enable a suitable conceptual thermal design. After screening various methods to heat the fixture, it was decided to use heating elements and thermal wires/IR sensors for the temperature regulation and control. Additionally, a sample cartridge was designed that prevents opening of the oven door in order to place a new sample on the support. Now, the three point bending measurements at elevated temperatures can be done much faster compared to the currently available set-ups, and also the temperature is recorded at the bottom of the sample.

1 INTRODUCTION

ABB provides power products along the entire power transmission chain. Starting with generators, where power is generated, the current usually passes through circuit breakers to prevent the damage of step-up power distribution transformers. From the transmission lines the voltage is transferred to lower distribution voltage levels for industrial (e.g. factories), transportation (e.g. railway) or domestic applications. Along this power transmission chain, materials are exposed to many demanding conditions; the following section describes some thermal mechanical requirements on composite materials in current ABB products:

- Filament wound hollow core insulators for bushing (Figure 1a)
- Filament wound tap changers for oil filled transformers (Figure 1b)
- Woven fabric for slot liner insulation (Figure 1c)

Figure 1: a) Hollow core insulator, b), tap changer, c) rotor slot insulation

In all power products, heat is generated as a result of Ohmic losses. For some applications the materials are exposed to 105 °C in transformer oil, for some other applications the components are operated at 155 °C in air. Furthermore, the parts are usually exposed to vibrations of the operating equipment or transportation as well as thermal shocks during the start in cold environments.

This requires to design a product such that besides electrical and environmental properties, also thermal and mechanical properties are determined. In [1], a comparison between the three-point bending and dynamical mechanical analysis for composite rotor slot insulation was performed and showed the importance of glass transition temperature on the material properties. Another test method for thermal mechanical properties is the determination of the heat deflection temperature. However, the characteristic values are not universally valid properties [2].

The following paper discusses a new tool that enables a much faster determination of the mechanical properties by three-point bending at increased temperatures up to 210 °C. The presented contribution is part of a bachelor thesis supervised by the Corporate Research Centre of ABB Switzerland and the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts.

2 STATE OF THE ART AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPT

Universal tensile testing machine manufacturers can provide the machine with a thermal chamber or oven. The testing set-up will be placed inside of the oven and hot-air ventilation heats up the oven and the test set-up. After reaching the specified temperature, the test can be performed in accordance with ISO 178 [3], ISO 14125 [4] or ASTM D790 [5]. In the DMA only flexural modulus properties (storage and loss modulus) are determined, while for the three-point bending in accordance to the previously mentioned standards the sample either delaminates or breaks, so also the flexural strength can be determined. After breakage or rupture of the sample at the end of the measurement, a new sample is placed in and the test temperature should be reached again. At various positions in the oven, the temperature during a test cycle was recorded (Figure 2a and b).

Figure 2: a) Set-up for three point bending, b) various positions in the oven for temperature recording

From Figure 3a, it can be observed that a long time (approx. 1.5 - 2 hours) is required in order to reach a steady test temperature at 180 °C. After replacing the test specimen by opening of the chamber door (at point 144 minutes in Figure 3b), another 20-30 minutes should be waited, before the sample, the three-point bending support and anvil have reached the required test temperature again.

Figure 3: a) Measured heating time of the oven from RT to 180 °C, b) temperature change during opening of the door to replace the sample

It is clear that a set of measurements at various temperatures is very time consuming with this kind of set-up.

The heating time could be reduced by heating the entire oven to higher temperatures, and then reduce the temperature to the set-temperature again. However, this means that the sample in the oven also is heated up to this high temperature and might get damaged. This sample is then not representing the test series anymore. It is also still not clear which parts have already reached the set temperature

In order to avoid such long waiting time which leads to expensive and time consuming tests, a concept was developed comprising a heated and temperature controlled testing fixture. The main idea hereby is that localized heating of the fixture (support and anvil) leads to minimized temperature gradients along the specimen and fixture. Additionally, the entire heating times need to be reduced to a few minutes and should be controllable within ± 2 °C of the set temperature. Additionally, the sample temperature needs to be recorded before each measurement. Furthermore, any suitable load cell should be able to be used, so that no restrictions by heavy and large adapter cylinder needs to be taken into account. The load cell itself should not be heated up during operation of the set-up.

At this point of the concept finite element simulations are needed to determine the requirements on the set-up. The questions that need to be answered are:

- Question 1: How large is the difference in heating time of the top of the support between convective heating up to 180 °C and localized heat generation in the support itself?
- Question 2: How is the temperature distribution within the sample, when is it placed on the fixture?

2.1 FEM-simulation – Definition of the geometry

The Comsol 5.0 software was used to perform these basic simulations. It is clear, that not all physical effects are taken into account (e.g. radiation, non-linearity in the material properties), but the order of magnitude should be provided by the simulations. A normal, physics controlled mesh was used and the support temperature was recorded on top of the support with the boundary probe function (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Meshed three-point bending support

2.2 FEM-simulation with convection and heat generation in the support structure

The currently used oven is a hot-air oven with forced convection, and the heat transfer coefficient h was determined analytically to be around 23 W/m²K. For free convection a heat transfer coefficient value of 5 W/m²K is used [6]. For the first estimation 100 W heating elements were positioned at the bottom support, and the heat transfer coefficient for forced convection was set to 23 W/m²K.

As can be seen in Figure 5, after already approx. 7 minutes the 180 °C have been already reached, by using heating elements of 100 W whereas the forced convection without heating elements needs approx. 60 minutes.

The difference between forced and free convection using the 100 W heating elements is approx. 2 minutes. Without the heating elements the difference is approx. 45 minutes to reach 120 °C only. It is clear that the local heat generation heats up the fixture much faster than the currently used fixture.

This heating time for the forced convection is a bit lower than the measured value (Figure 5), because simulation directly starts with an oven temperature of 180 °C and not at RT (time difference of 10 minutes). Additionally, the heavy adapters that are connected to the load cell are not included in the simulation.

Figure 5: Temperature elevation up to 180 °C at the top of the support under various conditions

The result of this study is that in case locally heat is generated in the fixture itself, the **heating time is reduced to the minutes range instead of one hour**. Forced convection heats up the fixture and sample faster than free convection (Figure 6a and b). It is clear that not the entire set-up has the same temperature, but at least where the temperature is required, namely at the support of the fixture and the anvil, the temperature is the set-temperature and can be controlled thereafter. In the final design, the heating elements are switched off after reaching the set temperature and controlled by the operating unit. Thus, the measurement can already be started although no steady state condition has been reached yet.

Figure 6: **a)** Temperature distribution of the set-up after 340 seconds ($h = 23 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, 100 W heating elements, oven at 180 °C) and **b)** Temperature distribution of the set-up after 460 seconds ($h = 5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, 100 W heating elements, oven at 180 °C)

2.3 FEM-simulation for the temperature distribution within the sample

The second topic that needs to be addressed, is the temperature distribution within the sample. In general, polymers and composites have low heat transfer coefficients compared to metals. A glass or aramid fiber reinforced composite with a fiber volume fraction of 0.55, has in fiber direction a value of 0.9 – 1.1 W/mK, perpendicular to the fiber direction the resin dominated value is approx. 0.3 – 0.4 W/mK. For power products also mineral filled cast resins are also used and have thermal conductivity values of 0.6 – 0.9 W/mK. As the heating of the fixture with heating elements is fast, the easiest case of the design would be to use heating elements only without oven around it. The sample will be heated by the support only. This case was also simulated (Figure 7a), and it is clear that the temperature distribution along the sample is not homogeneous in case an oven is not used for polymeric samples.

The difference between the part where the sample is in contact with the support and at the end of the sample, can be as large as 50 °C. Even with insulation material around the fixture the temperature distribution in the sample will not homogeneous. The same simulation has been performed for an aluminum specimen as well (Figure 7b). Here it is clear that the samples can be heated by the support only.

Figure 7: **a)** Temperature distribution of the set-up after 560 seconds (**no oven**, 100 W heating, thermal conductivity of the sample of $\lambda = 1 \text{ W/mK}$ (composite) and **b)** Temperature distribution of the set-up after 560 seconds (**no oven**, 100 W heating, thermal conductivity of the sample of $\lambda = 201 \text{ W/mK}$ (aluminum)

The forced convection from the oven is required to heat up the polymeric sample evenly. For the oven, it is sufficient to contain a heating element with thermal wire close to the sample and a ventilator in order to generate forced convection. This might be an existing thermal chamber as, but one can also build one. For the anvil the same conclusions as for the support are applicable.

2.4 Concept generation for a temperature controlled heated three point bending set-up

The performed FE-simulations show that the control circuit for polymeric composite samples should contain the following elements:

- Heatable anvil and heatable support with temperature sensor to enable controlling of the temperature
- Thermal chamber or oven with temperature sensor for the forced convection
- Sensor for the sample temperature recording

For the heating of the anvil and support several possibilities can be used:

- Heating elements made of steel
- Heating elements made of ceramics
- Infra-red heaters
- Induction heating of the fixture

After listing the advantages and disadvantages of heating the set-up, it was decided to select the heating elements made of steel as they are very suitable for controlling the temperature and as they are standard elements and cost-effective as well. The required heating power for the set-up is in the range of 100 – 250 W. However, the heating elements are not available in all required dimensions. Bent ones directly placed on the surface of the support would be most suitable, but are not available in steel. Ceramics ones can be made after custom requirements and are able to heat very fast, but are much more expensive then.

It is important that the temperature of the support and anvil is recorded close to the sample, so it can be adjusted by the heating elements. For the sample itself it is more difficult. Here, the temperature recording can be done either in contact with the sample or contactless. After a screening it was decided to use the contactless sensor as otherwise the samples need to be equipped with a thermal wire or some other method that might disturb the measurement. Finally, a temperature resistant infra-red sensor was found. This sensor will record the temperature at the mechanically relevant position, which is in the middle of the sample, where the bending takes place (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Position for the IR-sensor

The response and recording time of the sample is sufficiently fast (response time 150 ms). However, the IR sensor needs to be calibrated for the various conditions (e.g. temperature, surface reflection, emissivity) prior to the measurement.

Now all required components and their functions for the set-up are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Summarizing all required components and their functions

Component	Type of temperature sensor	Recording of temperature in the operating software	Temperature controllable
Anvil	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	yes
Support 1 (left)	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	yes
Support 2 (right)	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	yes
Oven	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	yes
Sample	Infra-red sensor	yes	no
Heating element 1 (support left)	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	no
Heating element 2 (support right)	Thermal wire (resistance)	yes	no

This means that the entire structure gets quite complex and a suitable control system is required. In order to operate the heatable set-up on various universal tensile testing machines, it is required to have a stand-alone solution which can be integrated in the operating testing machine software. This means that the thermal elements need to be controlled separately, but no several single manually operated controllers are to be used. For the control software a commercially available system is required as not everybody has development software with required licenses. It was decided to purchase a system based on SPS-controller with operation panel that might be extended with components in case required. This of course is also not cheap, but enables flexibility at least for the development stage.

3 RESULTS

After taking into account the various requirements of the applicable standards (e.g. sample dimensions, adjustable radius of the lower support, and adjustable support width) a first CAD-design was made. The design of the three-point bending fixture is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Construction of the three-point bending device

The supports of the lower fixture are equipped with both radii of 2.0 and 5.0 mm. Depending on the sample geometry, either the small or the large radius need to be selected and set-up on the base plate. The support width can be adjusted as well. The infra-red sensor is fixed and determines the sample temperature in the middle of the sample.

It was observed that during opening of the door of the chamber to position a new sample on the fixture (Figure 3b), the furnace and fixture temperature decreased much. To avoid this a sample loader cartridge to be placed within the chamber was needed. A procedure of how a new sample can be positioned is illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Procedure for the sample loader cartridge

In the starting position (1) all samples are piled up on top of each other and in the second position (2) a rocking lever tilts only one sample until this one is flat on the base plate (3). Then a slide feed moves the sample on the three-point bending support (4). After sliding back the feed, the starting position is restored again (5) and the next sample can be positioned on the three point bending fixture. All samples are placed in the cartridge and position in the chamber before testing starts (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Construction of sample loader

After the testing, pressurized air blows away the tested parts from the support, and the rocking lever mechanism places the next sample on the support. The heating plate in the cartridge heats up the samples already before they are placed on the support. After the complete series of 5 to 10 samples, a new sample loaded cartridge needs to be placed in the oven. The placing of the sample might be automated, so that the tests can be performed until the cartridge is empty. The drive for the lever is placed outside of the oven, so it is not heated up.

Finally, a modular oven was constructed which can be easily placed around the set-up for any type of universal testing machines. Currently various elements have been machined already. Figure 12 presents the heatable supports, the heatable anvil, the heating elements and the IR sensor.

Figure 12: Various elements that have been machined and assembled already

4 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

In applications where composites are exposed to elevated temperatures, it is important to determine the mechanical properties. Not only directly after the manufacturing of the material, but even more importantly after operation at the elevated conditions. This provides an indication for the life-time of the material. These tests are very time consuming especially when several temperature condition needs to be investigated, so a set-up needed to be developed that increased the testing speed of three-point bending testing at elevated temperatures.

By means of thermal FEM-simulations and the development of various concepts, an initial design for a heatable three-point bending fixture was constructed. The newly developed test set-up enables the accurate temperature determination of the fixture (support and anvil) and sample temperature by thermal sensors. Now the set-up can be operated much faster than the conventional oven as the temperature at the required location, namely at the radius of the support and at the radius of the anvil, is controlled accurately. The heating time for performing the first measurement can be reduced from 1 - 1.5 h to only a few minutes. Further samples can now be started already after a few minutes instead of approx. 15-20 minutes for the currently used set-up. Especially, with the heated sample cartridge, many samples can be tested within a much shorter time as the door of the chamber is not opened during the series.

The next steps in the work include the assembly of the already machined components and provide connection of the thermal sensors to the thermal control unit.

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